

Evaluating Offloading Strategies in the IoT Continuum: a simulation-based approach

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Abstract—Motivated by the proliferation of latency-sensitive and computation-intensive smart applications demanding for effective and efficient workload distribution, this paper presents an architecture and a simulation framework designed to jointly develop and evaluate advanced offloading strategy in the Computing Continuum (CC). Indeed, the decision of how, when and where to offload has significant implications on service performance and user experience, but, due to its complexity, it requires proper architectures (for supporting the required offloading mechanisms) coupled with simulators (for preliminarily and systemically evaluating all the many possible options under realistic, dynamic conditions). A case study related to a Healthcare Internet of Things (HIoT) scenario exemplifies the proposal and demonstrates how this twofold approach, namely combining architecture and simulation, plays a valuable role in the engineering of complex smart systems, despite often being overlooked in the literature.

Index Terms—Continuum Computing, Offloading, Simulation, IoT.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to meet the growing demand for low-latency, scalable, end-to-end service delivery, the **Continuum Computing** (CC) paradigm has recently emerged as a key solution by integrating decentralized, local resources with centralized, remote infrastructures [1]. This integration is especially critical in the context of the **Internet of Things (IoT)**, where devices are often severely constrained in terms of energy, processing, and storage capabilities, while users and applications increasingly demand real-time responsiveness and reliable performance. Healthcare IoT (HIoT) is a paradigmatic example of this tension: tiny, low-cost, battery-powered, sensor-based devices with limited capabilities are indeed responsible for executing services that are often critical (such as electrocardiogram analysis, fatigue monitoring, etc.) at support of operations

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supposed to be highly reliable and responsive, particularly when human health is directly involved [2].

To a greater extent than pure Edge or Cloud setups (that operate in more static, uniform, and predictable environments), **Offloading** is regarded as a fundamental mechanism in the CC, as it mitigates heterogeneity, dynamism, and the inherent limitations of resource-constrained devices by delegating computation and data processing to more capable nodes across multiple layers [3], [4]. However, to fully support offloading flexible in terms of *modality* and *target* across the system infrastructure, there is a need for (i) system architectures spanning across the continuum and able to support the implementation of different offloading strategies; and (ii) simulation frameworks for modeling and evaluating the overall system under realistic operational conditions and a variety of contextual factors such as network conditions, resource availability, latency requirements, and user mobility. Interestingly, despite the growing interest in CC, the majority of prior studies treat these two enabling building blocks as separate concerns: hence, such a siloed approach limits the ability to derive holistic, implementation-aware conclusions.

Therefore, in this paper, we argue that design and evaluation of IoT systems must be tightly coupled, especially in CC scenarios. By integrating a flexible system architecture with a simulation-driven framework, indeed, more informed and adaptive design choices can be taken and advanced offloading strategies tried and tests. Hence, after a brief discussion on fundamental concepts and a focused review of related work (*Section 2*), we provide the three main contributions of this paper: an **architectural blueprint** specifically designed to support efficient, context-aware offloading strategies (*Section 3.a*); a **simulation framework** (*Section 3.b*) coupled to the architecture and faithfully adapting to complex, fluctuating environments and applications; and, finally, a **HIoT case study** based on these elements where a comprehensive simulation campaign showcases the potential of our approach for supporting an informed design of the whole system (*Section 4*). The concluding remarks wrap up these contributions and briefly outline future works (*Section 5*).

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. The Continuum Computing and the IoT

CC [5] defines a unified and integrated computational environment that spans from resource-constrained IoT edge devices, through intermediate edge servers, to remote cloud infrastructures and high-performance computing systems. Unlike conventional computing paradigms, which either centralize tasks in the cloud or confine them to the edge, the CC enables the flexible and dynamic distribution of computation across all layers for meeting the strict requirements for low latency, context awareness, and localized responsiveness. This distribution has arisen in response to the explosive growth in data generated by IoT applications, where IoT devices are inherently heterogeneous and often operate under severe constraints in terms of processing power, memory, and energy. In such contexts, efficient resource management and intelligent task offloading become not just beneficial, but essential to ensure the system's responsiveness and scalability while balancing tradeoffs between latency, energy efficiency, and computational capacity [6].

However, the architectural flexibility of the continuum introduces significant challenges, especially in managing heterogeneity in both hardware and software components. In contrast to simpler edge- or cloud-only systems, the continuum requires complex orchestration mechanisms capable of handling distributed data flows, guaranteeing transparent and seamless data access, and dynamically adapting to context changes [1]. Indeed, resource allocation decisions within the continuum must account for multiple constraints—including device location, energy budgets, task priority, and computational capabilities—turning the optimization of offloading strategies into a multi-dimensional, and often NP-hard, problem. To address these challenges, recent research increasingly turns to AI-based and data-driven approaches while simulations remain the primary method of evaluation, though the tools vary [4].

B. Offloading in the Continuum: A 5W Formalization

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF THE 5W-AWARE OFFLOADING MODEL

W	Symbol(s)	Meaning
Who	T	The task to be offloaded
What	\mathcal{S}_T	Task type: Data, Function, Application
Where	$\mathcal{L}_T, \mathcal{D}_T$	Origin and direction of offloading
Why	\mathcal{C}_T	Optimization objectives: latency, energy, etc.
When	\mathcal{T}_T	Decision timing: Static or Dynamic

The 5W method is a well-known problem-framing and analysis technique, widely used across multiple fields (including systems analysis and requirements engineering [7]) to capture the full context of a situation by identifying who is involved, where it occurs, when it happens, why it matters, and what is taking place. According to such a technique, we define the **offloading decision** in the CC as a mapping function:

$$f_{\text{offload}} : \mathcal{X}_T \rightarrow L_{\text{target}}$$

where the input feature vector \mathcal{X}_T encodes the properties of task T , the entity to be offloaded — i.e., the **Who**:

$$\mathcal{X}_T = \left(\underbrace{\mathcal{S}_T}_{\text{What}}, \underbrace{(\mathcal{L}_T, \mathcal{D}_T)}_{\text{Where}}, \underbrace{\mathcal{C}_T}_{\text{Why}}, \underbrace{\mathcal{T}_T}_{\text{When}} \right)$$

and:

$$L_{\text{target}} \in \{\text{Device, Edge, Cloud}\}$$

In detail, as summarized in Table I:

- **Who:** The task T to be offloaded, whose properties are described hereinafter.
- **What:** $\mathcal{S}_T \in \{\text{Data, Function, Application}\}$ denotes the subject of the offloading operation, indicating the granularity of the computation offloaded T , i.e., raw data, a computational function, or an entire application.
- **Where:**
 - $\mathcal{L}_T \in \{\text{Device, Edge, Cloud}\}$, namely the native location of the task.
 - $\mathcal{D}_T \in \{\text{Horizontal, Vertical, Omnidirectional}\}$ indicating the offloading direction in the continuum between peers at the same level, across levels, or across all directions.
- **Why:** $\mathcal{C}_T = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n] \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a vector representing the **cost function** or **optimization objectives**, which may include, for example:
 - $c_i \in \{\text{Latency, Energy, Bandwidth, Monetary cost}\}$
- **When:** $\mathcal{T}_T \in \{\text{Static, Dynamic}\}$, pertaining the temporal scope of the decision, made at design time or runtime and based on real-time context.

The function f_{offload} may be implemented using a specific strategy, i.e., the decision-making methodology used to determine whether and where to offload the task:

$$\mathcal{M}_T \in \{\text{Analytical, Heuristic, ML-based, Rule-based}\}$$

This strategy influences how the mapping is realized, but is not required to be part of the function input if it is externally fixed or abstracted.

C. Related Work

In the last few years, several scientific papers focused on offloading strategies within the CC, exploring both static and dynamic decision-making approaches with different evaluation modalities (simulation, analytical, or real-world testbeds) and discussing, in some cases, also architectural components.

A first bunch of works focuses exclusively on static offloading, where decisions are derived in advance and do not adapt to runtime changes. Both [8] and [9] utilized CloudSim extensions to simulate different static offloading policies based on fixed latency thresholds, predicted mobility

and resource availability. No architectural details are discussed nor particular architectural considerations addressed. Similarly, [10] introduced an optimization model to allocate tasks across edge and cloud, with all the decisions computed offline and evaluated in MATLAB without system-level implementation.

A different approach is followed by another group of works, which, instead, use context-aware mechanisms like reinforcement learning, Markov Decision Process (MDP), or online optimization to make decisions at runtime. In particular, [11] and [12] propose an optimization-based framework within a custom simulator where the offloading decision is adapted at runtime according to queue lengths and latency constraints. The strategy reacts to dynamic changes in the edge and cloud environments, including fluctuating workloads, but limited discussion of architectural components are provided. Similarly, [13] proposes a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulation for the offloading problem and develop, in MATLAB, a multi-agent rollout mechanism for allocating the available resources in the various layers of an edge-cloud infrastructure. Authors of [14], [15] and [16], instead, set the offloading strategy as a model-free deep reinforcement learning-based distributed algorithm: the studies lack architectural insights although simulation results demonstrate a good effectiveness in handling dynamic environments. Differently, in [17] the offloading is modeled as a multi-user game inspired by the Nash equilibrium and evaluation is carried out through OMNeT++. Finally, [18] introduces an innovative architecture based on smart agents that solve the task offloading problem in autonomous IoT systems. Simulations were done using the framework ns3-gym aiming at considering very realistic IoT environments. Again, the particular architectural details are commonly overlooked by these papers.

With respect to these related work, whose main features are resumed in Table II, we first proposes an architecture aimed at supporting different offloading strategies, both static and dynamic. Then, we couple such an architecture with a rich, full-scale, simulation framework purposely designed for capturing the complexity of real-world IoT and CC, thus enabling the validation of theoretical design choices under realistic and dynamic conditions (that include mobility, network variability, and resource constraints). When coupled to a sound architectural design, in fact, the use of a simulator becomes particularly effective and it outperforms the usage of MATLAB or numerical analysis, as it allows seamless integration between system structures and simulated behaviors.

III. ARCHITECTURE AND SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

A. Architecture

Traditional IoT systems are commonly organized into three distinct layers, i.e., mobile device, Edge/Fog, and Cloud, where computational tasks are a-priori offloaded to specific target based on the resource capabilities (e.g., heavyweight tasks always to the Cloud, lightweight ones to the Edge) they expose at design time. This rigid, resource-driven stratification leads to workload distribution that is decided statically, often neglecting the context in which the system operates. As a

TABLE II
APPROACHES FOR DESIGNING OFFLOADING STRATEGY

Work	Arch. details	Evaluation Method	Tool
[8]	Partial	Simulation	iFogCloudSim
[9]	Partial	Simulation	EdgeCloudSim
[10]	No	Numerical Analysis	MATLAB
[11]	No	Numerical Analysis	Custom
[12]	Partial	Numerical Analysis	Custom
[13]	No	Numerical Analysis	MATLAB
[14]	No	Simulation	Custom
[15]	No	Simulation	Custom
[16]	No	Numerical Analysis	Python
[17]	Partial	Simulation	OMNeT++
[18]	Yes	Simulation	NS3
Our	Yes	Simulation	Custom

Fig. 1. The CC architecture with the Dynamic Task Orchestrator

result, such architectures lack the flexibility and responsiveness required by smart applications which demand adaptability, real-time processing, and privacy preservation.

To overcome these limitations and support the dynamic nature of task offloading in the CC, we propose a microservice-based [19] architecture composed of five, coordinated building blocks that operate across the device, Edge, and Cloud layers, each contributing to a cohesive framework capable of adaptive, context-aware resource management. As shown in Figure 1, at the core of the system is the *Dynamic Task Orchestrator*, a control unit responsible for real-time offloading decisions. This component (K3s with custom scheduler) evaluates multiple factors, including system state, task priority, and application constraints, to determine the most suitable execution node, whether that be a nearby Edge server or a remote Cloud node.

Supporting the orchestrator is the *Context Monitor and Profiler*, which continuously gathers metrics on CPU load, memory usage, network latency, and energy levels across

the continuum. This module (Prometheus Node Exporter and Telegraf) ensures that decisions are not based on static assumptions but reflect the current state of the system. The profiler's insights are critical for enabling dynamic offloading strategies that adjust in response to environmental changes or resource contention.

Application constraints are formally described and enforced by the *QoS Policy Engine*: this module (Open Policy Agent OPA) maintains a catalog of service-level objectives (such as maximum tolerable latency, minimum throughput, or availability levels) and it translates these high-level requirements into actionable policies that guide the Dynamic Task Orchestrator, so as to ensure the alignment between offloading strategies and application goals.

Resource visibility and coordination across distributed nodes are instead achieved through the *Resource Manager and Service Registry*, which keeps track of the availability and capabilities of all compute and network nodes across the continuum. This component (Native K3s registry) enables the orchestrator to make informed placement decisions, ensuring that selected targets are not only appropriate in terms of proximity, but also capable of meeting the performance and resource needs of the offloaded tasks.

To close the control loop, the system incorporates a *QoS Feedback Loop*, which evaluates the actual performance of executed tasks against their expected QoS profiles. If a violation is detected (for example, excessive service time or failure rate) the QoS Feedback Loop (Redpanda) can trigger a reallocation of tasks or update future scheduling decisions. This continuous feedback mechanism supports both corrective and predictive adaptation, making the architecture resilient and responsive.

Together, these components form an integrated and modular architecture that enables dynamic task offloading across a heterogeneous, large-scale infrastructure and, unlike static schemes which rely on predefined mappings between tasks and compute nodes, it adapts to system variability in real time. Moreover, the architecture components well map with the formal offloading operation provided in Section 2.B. Indeed, both the granularity of offloading, denoted by ST and the timing of offloading decisions, TT , are governed by the *Dynamic Task Orchestrator*, which defines whether raw data, computational functions, or entire applications are offloaded based on contextual inputs or static policies. The native location of the task, LT , is managed by the *Resource Manager and Service Registry*, which tracks where tasks originate and the potential execution nodes across the continuum. The offloading direction, DT , is derived from observations by the *Context Monitor and Profiler*, which characterizes network and resource conditions to support dynamic selection among horizontal, vertical, or omnidirectional offloading paths. Cost functions and optimization objectives, CT , are encoded in the *QoS Policy Engine*, guiding the trade-off analysis that underpins offloading decisions to satisfy latency, energy, bandwidth, or other constraints.

B. Simulation Framework

The principles and building blocks of the proposed system architecture are inherently mirrored in the simulation framework.

Event-driven, modular and Java-based, it enables the deployment and coordination of applications across the CC according to the profiles of the available nodes (computation power, energy, etc.) and the characteristics/requirements of application tasks. Defining characteristics of modern IoT scenarios are fully accommodated in the simulator: user mobility is fully integrated, allowing devices to follow various mobility patterns and experience corresponding shifts in connectivity, migration overheads, and handover strategies; the effects of network variability, including fluctuating latency and bandwidth, intermittent connectivity, and packet losses (which are crucial for accurately modeling IoT environments where communication is often unstable), are captured; resource constraints and heterogeneity such as limited battery capacity, different CPU power, just to name the main ones, are explicitly modeled. Just its compatibility with IoT-specific constraints makes the simulation framework particularly effective for the modeling of realistic deployment scenarios in the CC as well as for the implementation and evaluation of offloading strategies of different complexities involving entire applications, discrete functions, or data blocks. In particular, the simulation framework significantly extends EdgeCloudSim [20] (which stands out as a comprehensive yet extensible simulation tool with a multi-layer organization) by integrating the architectural abstraction needed a omnidirectional, fine-grained offloading decision guided by real-time system-level metrics such as energy, latency, and network conditions. The workflow for operating with the simulation framework, instead, remained unchanged and proceeds as follows:

- 1) Definition (by means of XML templates) of the characteristics of the simulation environment, such as the number and type of nodes, user mobility patterns, network settings, traffic characteristics, application types and related parameters. The *Resource Manager and Service Registry* aligns with the XML-based setup of nodes, networks, and applications. The *Context Monitor and Profiler* informs which dynamic parameters (e.g., mobility, workload) should appear in the simulation traces;
- 2) Selection, among the predefined offloading strategies catalog, of the ones to be tested or definition a new one. The *Dynamic Task Orchestrator* maps directly to the Java offloading policy class, executing decisions based on the current context, while the *QoS Policy Engine* enforces the latency, energy, or performance constraints;
- 3) Simulation run and analysis of the output files. The *QoS Feedback Loop* analyzes simulation outputs across runs to refine strategy parameters while the *Context Monitor* captures simulated runtime variations, enabling adaptive behavior within the orchestrator logic. Finally, because the simulator supports automated batch executions and

Fig. 2. The considered HIoT scenario: 4 Edge Server and the Cloud

parameter sweeps, horizontal and vertical scalability studies are carried out efficiently and comprehensively.

Following this workflow, the simulation framework enables systematic and controlled experimentation across a wide range of system setups, algorithmic strategies, and infrastructure deployments, enabling a rapid exploration and refinement of design alternatives. Hence, by effectively bridging architectural abstraction with operational realism, the framework proves to be a powerful tool for simulation-driven development of IoT systems in the CC.

IV. SMART HEALTHCARE CASE STUDY

In the context of HIoT, let us consider important smart applications aimed at improving, in mobility, remote monitoring and diagnostics for patients with different medical needs. In particular, the proposed case study shown in Fig. 2 involves patients equipped with wearable devices and/or smartphones that collect physiological data to be processed by the doctors of a Smart Hospital through Edge and Cloud Computing infrastructures. To support scalability and efficient service delivery, four Edge Servers are strategically deployed to cover different areas of the city. A *Dynamic Task Orchestrator*, supported by the *Context Monitor and Profiler*, the *Resource Manager and Service Registry*, and the *QoS Policy Engine*, instead, coordinates the data flow and computation across Edge and Cloud layers so as to balance situations in which a given Edge Server is unable to process all its incoming requests. This decentralized infrastructure improves the responsiveness and robustness of the system, especially in urban settings with high and variable patient density. The system supports three representative smart applications, each of which is aligned with a specific offloading granularity:

- **AI-Powered Skin Lesion Analyzer (SLA).** This mobile application allows patients, by using their smartphone camera, to capture high-resolution images of skin lesions: these will be analyzed using deep learning models to detect potential dermatological issues (e.g., risk of melanoma by). Due to the high image resolution and

computational complexity of running convolutional neural networks, this application benefits from *Application Offloading*. Indeed, the entire processing workflow (including image preprocessing, inference, and risk assessment) is offloaded to Edge or Cloud servers, relieving the smartphone from heavy computation and battery drain.

- **Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) Data Sync.** Patients with diabetes use wearable CGM sensors that log glucose levels, periodically offloading them for aggregation, trend analysis, and dashboard reporting. Since the data are time-series and computational requirements are minimal, this scenario is typical of *Data Offloading* because the mobile application mainly collects and uploads data without performing significant processing locally.
- **Smart Cough Analysis (SCA)** Designed to aid in the early detection of respiratory conditions, this application records short audio samples of a patient's cough through the smartphone's microphone. It locally performs basic preprocessing such as noise filtering and segmentation, while the more intensive task of feature extraction and pattern classification (e.g., detecting COVID-19-like symptoms or bronchitis) is offloaded. With moderate data size and partial computation, this scenario fits *Function Offloading*, as only specific parts of the processing pipeline are delegated to external nodes.

According to these descriptions, the following six offloading strategies (three static and three dynamic) are encoded in the *QoS Policy Engine*. In the **Only Edge**, all tasks originating from patient devices are offloaded exclusively to Edge Servers, both local (close to the user) and remote Edge Servers (deeper in the local network), but the Cloud is never involved. Conversely, tasks are always offloaded to Cloud resources, bypassing Edge Servers entirely, in the **Only Cloud**. Instead, in **Balanced**, a fixed workload distribution with offloading equally addressed towards Edge Servers and the Cloud. For what pertains the dynamic offloading strategies, **Location-Aware** prioritizes proximity by first attempting to offload tasks to the local Edge Server and, if unavailable or overloaded, tasks are redirected to a remote Edge Server, or finally, to the Cloud as a fallback. In **Time-Aware**, the system continuously monitors the estimated service time, intended as the sum of computation and network latency, of all available execution nodes and each task is dynamically routed to the Edge or Cloud with the lowest predicted service time. Finally, the **Fault-Aware** aims at maximizing reliability and dynamically assigns tasks to the node (Edge or Cloud) with the lowest historical or predicted failure rate.

Obviously, additional offloading strategies can be added or these ones further enhanced through hybrid or multi-criteria strategies but, even in their basic form, they highlight the trade-offs between responsiveness, reliability, and computational efficiency in offloading decisions. Indeed, the goal of the simulation is not to identify the optimal offloading strategy, but to showcase the potential of the architecture and the simulation framework, as well as the value added of an informed design

decision for simulation-based engineering, regardless of a specific application domain. Therefore, we carried out a comprehensive simulation campaign by testing the overall system performance when the static/dynamic offloading strategies and the number of patients vary, considering the hardware and network setup summarized in Table III.

TABLE III
SUMMARY OF HARDWARE AND NETWORK SETUP

Component	CPU (Cores)	RAM	Network Link
Edge Server	16 x x86	64 GB	LAN/WAN (5 Gbps)
Cloud Server	64 x x86	1 TB	Backbone (100 Gbps)
Latency (avg)	Device-Edge: 10–30 ms, Edge-Cloud: 15–30 ms		

A. Results Analysis

We consider a 3-hours simulation where, within the monitored population of 1000 patients, only a variable ratio (from 10 to 99 “active” users) simultaneously requires for a task offloading, while moving according to a random pattern. We hypothesize three different scenarios: the probability distribution is uniform among the applications, i.e., each patient’s request has the same probability to refer to SLA, CGM or SCA (Scenario 1); the patients are more likely to request CGM or SCA (40% each) rather than SLA (20%, Scenario 2); offloading requests for CGM are predominant (80%) and the remaining are equally referred to SLA and SCA (10% each, Scenario 3). It is important to note that the requests have the same priority and occur with a Poisson interarrival of 30 seconds. These simulation parameters are also shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value / Description
Simulation Time	3 hours
Total Population	1000 patients
Active Users	Up to 10% [10-99 patients]
Mobility Pattern	Random mobility model
Interarrival Time	Poisson, 30 seconds
Request Priority	Identical
Offloading Distribution	Scenario1: Uniform across SLA, CGM, SCA Scenario2: CGM=40%, SCA=40%, SLA=20% Scenario3: CGM=80%, SLA=10%, SCA=10%

With respect to Scenario 1, Figure 3 shows that, among the static offloading strategies, the “Only Edge” suffer significant performance degradation as the number of active patients increases (with service times exceeding 70 seconds and failure rates surpassing 70% under high load), hence reflecting severe resource saturation at Edge Server. The “Balanced” strategy offers moderate responsiveness but exhibits poor tolerance to failure when scaling. Conversely, since the computation and data traffic are both relevant in this first scenario, the “Only Cloud” strategy maintains lower service times and service

failures, with performance close to the dynamic offloading strategies.

The situation changes in Scenarios 2 and 3 where, in contrast, adaptive offloading strategies demonstrate superior scalability and resilience for workload less computation-intensive. In particular, as Figure 4 shows, “Time-Aware” and “Location-Aware” achieves overall the best performance, while “Only Edge” performs adequately at every stress levels and “Only Cloud” suffers from bottleneck effects (“Balanced” shows, as expected, intermediate values). Finally, in Figure 5, it can be noticed that offloading strategies that consider host resilience (“Fault-Aware”) or proximity (“Location-Aware”) offer significantly better robustness under high load conditions, while “Time-Aware” strategies may prioritize speed at the expense of stability; conversely, static strategies (e.g., “Only Edge” or “Balanced”) suffer high failure rates due to lack of adaptability.

The obtained results, albeit confirm well-known trends, should be interpreted not as an attempt to outperform existing offloading strategies but as a demonstration of the broader potential of the development approach coupling a flexible system architecture with simulation-based exploration, providing precious, informed, evidence-driven design decisions. Indeed, by coding desired requirements (e.g., service time deadline or failure rate) within the QoS Police Engine, any “what-if” analysis and scalability test can be performed for preliminary discarding unsuitable offloading strategies or system configurations before the deployment.

V. CONCLUSION

While the CC offers a promising paradigm for supporting complex, latency-sensitive, and distributed IoT applications, it also exposes an urgent need for fine-grained resource management and intelligent task offloading strategies that extend well beyond the scope of traditional Edge or Cloud computing. The current literature reflects a growing trend toward dynamic and intelligent offloading, although system architectures and evaluation methods (numerical analysis and simulators) are often separately developed. This separation results in partial insights that may not fully capture the interplay between system design choices and operational performance in CC scenarios. On these basis, in this paper we have proposed an approach combining a flexible architecture with a coupled simulation framework to guide informed design choices across varied deployment scenarios in the CC. An use case has been finally discussed: simulation results, on the one hand, confirmed that dynamic offloading strategies are better suited to the continuum inherent variability but demand more complex runtime support, but, more importantly, showcased the broader potential of our approach.

On-going developments are aimed at addressing some of the current limitations of the work: *validation*, for matching obtained results with real-world behavior (e.g., bursty tasks generation and structured mobility patterns) in different application domains; and *replication/distribution* of the Dynamic

Fig. 3. Scenario 1: uniform probability distribution among application, data and function offloading

Fig. 4. Scenario 2: 80% of data and function offloading

Task Orchestrator (and its components) across different nodes, for the sake of robustness and scalability.

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Fig. 5. Scenario 3: 80% of data offloading

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